

Environmental Protection and Contribution of Indian Judiciary through Public Interest Litigation

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Abstract

"I would feel more optimistic about a bright future for man if he spent less time proving that he can outwit Nature and more time tasting her sweetness and respecting her seniority."

..... E.B. White

One of the most burning topic in the international as well as national scenario, today is the relationship between economic development accompanied with the desire for maximization of profits and ruthless competitiveness and the rapid deterioration of environment. Failure on the part of the governmental agencies to effectively enforce environmental laws and non-compliance with statutory norms by polluters resulted in an accelerated degradation of the environment. Environmental Jurisprudence has been a considerable share of initiative by the Indian judiciary with the relaxation of the rule of "Locus Standi" and the departure from the "Proof of injury" approach which has created a new form of legal action termed as Public Interest litigation (PIL) which is usually more efficient in dealing with environmental cases as these cases are concerned with the rights of the community rather than the individual. PIL is the result of judicial activism. The present paper attempts to analyze the dynamism and the spirit of protection of environment displayed by Indian Judiciary through PIL.

Keywords: Environment, Indian Judiciary, PIL, Judicial Activism

Introduction

According to Indian Law, PIL means a mode of litigation, which is carried out for protection of public interest. This type of litigation is introduced in a court of law, where the court itself takes cognizance or by any other private party and not by the aggrieved party. There are diverse areas where a public interest litigation can be filed. For e.g. ...

- When basic human rights of a poor person is violated.
- To question contents or conduct of any government policy.
- To compel municipal authorities to perform a public duty.
- When religious rights or other basic fundamental rights are violated.

Historical Development

Prior to 1980's, only the aggrieved party was able to knock the door of justice personally and can see remedy for his grievance and any other person was not entitled to represent that victim or the aggrieved party. In other words only aggrieved party was having locus standi to file a case and continue the litigation and the non-affected persons were not having locus standi to do so.

However, this entire scenario gradually change post emergency period when Supreme Court tackle the problem of access to justice to people through radical changes and alterations were made in the requirements of Locus standi and of aggrieved party.

The splendid efforts of Justice P.N. Bhagwati and Justice Krishna Iyer were instrumental of this juristic revolution of eighties to convert the Apex Court of India into a Supreme Court of all Indians.

First of all issue of Public Interest Litigation was taken by Justice V.R. Krishna Iyer in *Akhil Bharatiya Soshit Karmchhari Sangh vs. Union of India AIR 1981 SC 298* in which an unregistered association of workers was permitted by the Supreme Court to institute a writ petition under Article 32 for the redressal of a common grievance and in *S.P. Gupta vs Union of India AIR 1982 SC 149* it was firmly established by Justice P.N. Bhagwati.

Importance of PIL

Public Interest Litigation provides a wider interpretation to the right to equality, life and personal liberty which is provided by part III of the Constitution of India. It has also introduced some types of reliefs or remedies under the writ jurisdiction. It also functions as an effective instrument to bring changes in the society or social welfare. Through PIL, any public or person can seek remedy on behalf of the oppressed class introducing a PIL.

Role of PIL in Development of Environmental Jurisprudence or Enviro-Judicial Remedies

Professor Upendra Baxi, who has often supported the judicial activism in India, has also said that the “Supreme Court of India” has often become “Supreme Court for Indians”. Power and judicial activism of the Indian Courts have resulted into a strong and ever expanding regime of fundamental rights. Stockholm Conference on Human Environment 1972 has generated a strong global international awareness and in India it facilitated the enactment of the 42nd Constitutional Amendment, 1976. This amendment introduced certain environmental duties both on the part of citizens Article 51 A (g) and on the State Article 48 (A). Moreover, these provisions have been used by the Courts to justify and develop a legally binding fundamental right to environment as a part of right to life under Article 21.

Before 1996 there were very few references to international environmental treaties though by 1990 India was party to more than 70 multilateral treaties of environmental significance. In *Asbestos Industries Case* the Supreme Court extensively quoted many international laws namely ILO Asbestos Convention 1986, Universal Declaration of Human Rights 1945 and International Convention of Economic, Social and Cultural Rights 1966.

Important Landmark Judgments on Environment Protection by Judiciary

- **Rural Litigation and Entitlement Kendra, Dehradun vs. State of U.P. AIR 1985 SC 652**

The Rural Litigation and Entitlement Kendra, on the behalf of residents of the Doon Valley, filed a case in the Supreme Court against limestone quarrying. This case was the first requiring the Supreme Court to balance environmental and ecological integrity against industrial demands on forest resources. The Court directed the authorities to stop quarrying in the Mussoorie hills.

- **Shriram Gas Leak Case AIR 1987 SC 965**

In the historic case of the oleum gas leak from the Shriram Food and Fertilizer Factory in Delhi in 1986, the Supreme Court ordered the management to pay compensation to the victims of the gas leak. The absolute liability of the hazardous chemical manufacturer to give compensation to all those affected by an accident was introduced in this case and it was the first time compensation was paid to victims.

- **Subhash Kumar vs. State of Bihar AIR 1991 SC 420**

It has been held that PIL is maintainable for ensuring enjoyment of Pollution free water and air which is included in the right of life under Article 21 of the constitution.

- **M.C. Mehra vs. Union of India AIR 1985 SC 965**

Activist – Advocate M.C. Mehta filed a writ petition in the Supreme Court to highlight the pollution of the Ganga by industries and Municipalities located on its bank. The Court ordered the closure of a number of polluting tanneries near Kanpur.

- **Pradeep Krishan vs. Union of India and others AIR 1996 SC 204**

The petitioner, has filed a petition under Article 32, challenging the validity and constitutionality of an order issued by the State of Madhya Pradesh, permitting collection of tender leaves from sanctuaries and National Parks by the villagers living around the boundaries thereof with the villagers living around the boundaries thereof with the avoided object of maintenance of their traditional rights. The order of Court is that, there can be no doubt that urgent steps must be taken to prevent any destruction or damage to the environment.

- **M.C. Mehta vs. Union of India AIR 1996 USCC 750**

A PIL was filed by M.C. Mehta under Capital Region Act 1985 called National Planning Board which a very grim picture emerges regarding increase of pollution in the city of Delhi. The Supreme Court directed the Central Pollution Control Board to issue individual notices to all those 8378 industries which are polluting industries and are operating in non-confirming areas in violation of the Delhi Master Plan formulated under the Delhi Development Authority Act 1957, Delhi Municipal Corporation Act 1957 and the Factories Act 1948.

- **Rounaq International Limited vs. IVR Construction AIR 1999 SC 393**
In the words of Court, any interim order which stops the project from proceeding further must reimburse all the cost to the public in case ultimately litigation started by such an individual or body fails.
- **Vellore Citizens Welfare Forum vs. Union of India & Others AIR 1996 SC**
The petitioner filed a PIL under Article 32 of Constitution against the large scale pollution caused to River Polar due to discharge of untreated effluents by the tanneries and other industries in the State of Tamil Nadu. The Court delivering its judgment in favour of petitioners.

Many more such cases could be added from the history of Indian judiciary which are more vocal in support of environment and healthy life than other pillars of Indian Democracy.

- **Municipal Council, Ratlam Vs. Shri Vardhichand – Water pollution case Ratlam AIR 1980 SC 1622**
The Supreme Court instructed the Municipal Corporation of Ratlam to follow the order of Sub Divisional Magistrate of Ratlam City and take necessary steps to protect the area from pollution due to alcohol plant flowing. The court also said it can raise its demand of financial support from the State Government.
- **M.C. Mehta Vs. Union of India – Ganga Pollution Case AIR 1988 SC 1087**
The court highlighted the importance of certain provisions which protect our environment. Article 48 – A also made sure that the State will take right steps to protect and safeguard wildlife of the country. The court stated the importance of Water (Prevention and Control of Pollution) Act, 1974 (The Water Act) which helps maintain water quality. In the historic judgment of 1987, the court said that “Just like an industry which cannot pay minimum wages to its workers should not be allowed to exist, a tannery which cannot set up a primary treatment plant should not be allowed to continue its existence.
- **M.C. Mehta Vs. Kamal Nath & Ors – The diversion of river Beas case 1997 ISLC 388**
In this case the Supreme Court held that the forest lands which are given on lease to the Motel by the State Government are situated at the bank of river Beas. The area is ecologically fragile and therefore should not be converted into private ownership. Doctrine of Public Trust was applied in this case and held that the properties like river, seashore, forests and the air cannot be used for general public. The Motel was asked to pay compensation and construct a boundary wall with a distance of not more than 4 meters. The Court also restricted the Motel from discharging untreated effluent into the river and asked HP Pollution Board to keep a check on it.
- **Samit Mehta Vs. Union of India – Marine Pollution case due to ship sinking MANU/GT/0104/2016**
National Green Tribunal held that ship sinking accident has led to the marine pollution. Therefore, environmental compensation of Rs. 100 crores was imposed. It is one of the biggest compensation ever made by the private entity to Government.
- **Almitra H. Patel & Ors. Vs. Union of India – Municipal garbage disposal case 1998 2-SCL 416**
A complete prohibition on open burning of waste on lands was made after this, including landfills.
- **Vanashakti and 4 others Vs. Union of India and 11 Others (4 October, 2019)**
In this case, a PIL was filed in Bombay High Court in order to protect the remaining forests of Aarey situated in Mumbai which were to be cut for construction purpose. Many environmentalists as well as the social activists opposed the orders of the Government and went to the court although, the court disregarded the contentions considering the facts and circumstances of the cases.
- **Bombay Environmental Action Group Vs. The State of Maharashtra and Others (17 September, 2018)**
In this case, the destruction of mangroves in the state of Maharashtra was in issue and a PIL was filed in this regard in the Bombay High Court. Mangrove Ecosystem forms an important part of the habitat and hence, the court held that it is the obligation of the state to restore these mangrove areas and a committee was also formed in order to look into this matter.
- **Kalia Sethi and Another Vs. State of Odisha and Others (9 August, 2017)**
In this case, the role National Green Tribunal in cases involving environmental issues was discussed. The High Court of Odisha held that National Green Tribunal was established in order to take care of the Environmental laws and make sure that in case there is violation, it can take the cognizance of the offense.

Reasons for Judicial Activism in Protection of Environment

The year 1972 holds significance for the Environment jurisprudence as it has changed the course of action altogether. The Stockholm conference is milestone from where this country and other developing countries have to look environment from different perspective.

The Government of India was though signatory at later stage but strong votary of protection as agreed upon. Before the pro-active role of Indian judiciary, Government had no mechanism to deal with such situations.

No comprehensive law existed prior to 1986. Environment Protection Act came into existence in 1986 after 14 years of Stockholm conference. Though Water Act 1974 and Air 1981 were there but they were insufficient to deal with. Indian judiciary have got the necessary impetus from Civil Society's activism in environment protection. Environment jurisprudence shaped by the Indian judiciary within the Indian Constitution is the major achievement after Stockholm Conference.

The judiciary made several attempts to resolve the conflict between the development and environment. The environmental jurisprudence in India developed through the instrument of Public Interest Litigation (PIL).

Conclusion

Public Interest Litigation has been used by the Courts as an effective tool in dealing with cases involving Environmental issues. The courts must ensure that the use of PIL for private interests should not be entertained because it defeats the very purpose of this concept. Serving the public at large is the most important characteristic of PILs.

Also it is the duty of every citizen to take care of the environment and have compassion towards living creatures according to Article-51(g) of the Constitution of India. PIL under Article-32 and Article-226 must be invoked whenever there is any breach of duty.

Ultimately, it is the court who decides whether a case requires a hearing or how much graver is the offence. But, PIL plays a major role in delivering justice not only to the one who is involved in the case but to the community at large protecting the cumulative rights of all.

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